

Paper 2

**LIFE SKILL - A DYNAMIC MUTI-DIMENSIONAL PROCESS
ENCOMPASSING HUMAN DEVELOPMENT**

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ABSTRACT

Education is the most important instrument for human resource development. Education has been regarded as both an end in itself and as a means of realizing other desirable ends. It develops the personality and rationality of individuals, qualifies them to full fill certain economic, political and cultural functions and there by improve their socio-economic status. Education is an instrument of socialization is considered as a powerful catalytic agent for social change. Hence quality education and empowerment of youth are very much needed in the context of Globalization, Liberalization and Internationalization. An effective educational system is an essential foundation to lead a decent life. The Indian youth is currently at crossroads. India has been facing the challenges in providing quality education to the youth. The issues of financing, management, equity, and relevance, reorientation of programmes for laying emphasis on values and ethics and quality of higher education all are of severe concern at the present situation. The mobility of skilled manpower increased with globalization and Indian education system also evolved into knowledge-based society. Demands of contemporary life, under privileged parenting, dysfunctional relations, changing family structure, new perspectives of young people's needs, speedy socio-cultural changes all makes it crucial for a life skill education. Life skills are defined as the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour enables individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. The world health organization (WHO) defined life skill as abilities to face the day to day complex situations successfully and adjust with them efficiently. It identifies ten life skills that are very much needed to lead a healthy and happy life, so that all the human resources can be utilized effectively and productively. They are: Problem solving skills, Critical thinking skills, Creative thinking skills, Decision making skills, Effective communication skills, Inter personal relationship skills, Self-awareness skills, Empathy, Skills to cope with emotions and Skills to cope with stress. Life skill education can help to improve the well-being of individuals. The life skills are to be developed in the process of education. This life skills enable a person to live his life effectively purposefully, successfully and meaningfully. When knowledge is learned passively, without skills, it is often learned at a superficial level and therefore not readily transferred to new environments, deep understanding and accountability for the real world will occur

only by embedding skills within knowledge domain, such that each enhances the other. In the present social scenario skills are the key to solving economic, civic, and global challenges and to engaging effectively in those spheres, then we must act upon the belief that using those skills to overhaul our education system is possible.

Introduction

Education is the most important instrument for human resource development. Education has been regarded as both an end in itself and as a means of realizing other desirable ends. It develops the personality and rationality of individuals, qualifies them to fulfill certain economic, political and cultural functions and thereby improve their socio-economic status. It has been recognized as a major instrument which society can use to direct the process of change and development towards the desired goals. It provides for vertical mobility and can thereby help to equalize status between individuals coming from different social strata. In Indian way of thinking, a human being is a positive asset and precious national resource, which needs to be cherished, nurtured and developed with tenderness and care coupled with dynamism. Education is a unique investment in the present and in the future.

Life Skill Education: The Need of The Hour

According to Dr.S. Radhakrishnan “Education is not merely a means of earning a living, nor is it only a nursery of thought or a school for citizenship. It is initiation into the life of spirit, a training of human souls in the pursuit of truth and the practice of virtue”. Education is an instrument of socialization is considered as a powerful catalytic agent for social change. Hence quality education and empowerment of youth are very much needed in the context of Globalization, Liberalization and Internationalization. An effective educational system is an essential foundation to lead a decent life. India being a vast and diverse country, the Indian youth is slowly undergoing a cultural transition in their outlook due to globalization, communication, media and technological advancement. The Indian youth is currently at crossroads. India has been facing the challenges in providing quality education to the youth. The issues of financing, management, equity, and relevance, reorientation of programmes for laying emphasis on values and ethics and quality of higher education all are of severe concern at the present situation. Demands of contemporary life, under privileged parenting, dysfunctional relations, changing family structure, new perspectives of young people’s needs, speedy socio-cultural changes all makes it crucial for a life skill education. As far as swami Vivekananda is concerned “We want that education by which character is formed, strength of mind is increased, the intellect is expanded by which one can stand on one’s feet, Education is the manifestation of perfection already in man.”

Democracies need active, informed responsible citizens, who are willing and able to take responsibility for themselves and their communities and contribute to the political process. Life skill education can be beneficial in targeting negative behaviours in children and encouraging sound values and actions. Life skill involve a long-term process that is sustained overtime through regular and varied activities. Life skill education focuses on equipping individuals with skills relevant and appropriate which can prepare them to be successful at the world of work,by developing life skills in adolescents leads right attitude and values in to healthy behaviour.

Meaning of Life Skills

Life skills are defined as the abilities for adaptive and positive behaviour enables individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life. The world health organization (WHO) defined life skill as abilities to face the day to day complex situations successfully and adjust with them efficiently. It identifies ten life skills that are very much needed to lead a healthy and happy life, so that all the human resources can be utilized effectively and productively. They are:

- Problem solving skills
- Critical thinking skills
- Creative thinking skills
- Decision making skills
- Effective communication skills
- Inter personal relationship skills
- Self-awareness skills
- Empathy
- Skills to cope with emotions
- Skills to cope with stress

The above-mentioned life skills can be described in the following way

Problem solving skills: The ability to identify the problem correctly, understanding its sources and causes is the first step in solving problem. Later the causes have to be reduced or eliminated at the first stage. Then the source of the problem has to be handled carefully. Afterwards the best possible solution can be adopted.

Critical thinking skills: It is a skill of estimation of positive and negative dimensions of an experience or event without the influence of personal bias. Critical thinking is an ability to analyses information and experiences in an objective manner. It can contribute to health by helping us to

recognizes and assess the factors that influence attitude and behaviours such as values, peer pressures and the media.

Creative thinking skills: The ability to form new and original from the available information is creative thinking or divergent thinking. It is a novel way of seeing or doing things that is characteristics of four components: fluency (generating new ideas), flexibility (shifting perspective easily), originality (conceiving of something new) and elaboration (building another ideas).

Decision making skills: Decision making involves taking an appropriate decision after weighing the advantages and disadvantages of a situation and its future consequences. It helps us to deal constructively with decision about our lives.

Effective communication skills: It is the ability to convey the intended thoughts, ideas, feeling and expectations and plans meaningfully, politely and assertively to others. It implies that we are able to express ourselves both verbally and non -verbally in ways that are appropriate to our cultures and situations.

Interpersonal relationship skills: It is the maintenance of friendly, healthy purposeful and successful social relationship with others. It helps us to relate in positive ways with the people we interact with. This may mean being able to make and keep friendly relationships which can be of great importance to our mental and social well-being.

Self-awareness skills: It is the ability to know one's strengths and weaknesses, objectively and ones likes and dislikes, attitude correctly. That means knowing one-self as he or she is. It is often a pre-requisite to effective communication and interpersonal relations as well as for developing empathy with others.

Empathy: Is the ability to imagine oneself in the position of another person and to feel understand that persons happiness and sorrows. To have a successful relationship with our loved ones and society at large we need to understand and care about other people's needs, desire and feelings. when we understand ourselves as well as others, we are better prepared to communicate our needs and desires. We will be more equipped to say what we want people to know, present our thoughts and ideas and tackle delicate issues without offending other people, empathy can help us to accept others, who may be very different from ourselves.

Skills to cope with emotions: Coping with emotion is the ability to express one's emotions rationally taking the surrounding circumstances into considerations. Involving recognizing emotions within us

and others, being aware of how emotions influence behaviour and being able to respond to emotions appropriately.

Skills to cope with stress: Coping with stress is the ability to relieve one's stress constructively without affecting one's morale. It means recognizing the sources of stress in our lives, recognizing how this affects us and acting in ways that help us to control our level of stress, by changing our environment or life style and learning how to relax.

The following are the skills to cope with stress.

- Taking deep breath accompanied by thoughts of being in control.
- Progressive muscle relaxation
- Setting small goals and breaking tasks into smaller manageable chunks
- Focusing on things you can control and letting go of things you cannot control
- Exercising regular meals and avoiding excessive caffeine.
- Talking about problems with others including parents, older adults and friends
- Lowering unrealistic expectations.
 - Scheduling breaks and enjoyable activities such as music, arts, sports, socializing.

Life skills facilitate individuals to interpret information, attitude and principles into definite abilities that is “what to do and how to do it.” Life skills are abilities that makes possible persons to act in healthy ways, given the desire, capacity and opportunity to do so.

Essentials of life skill

The Dakar frame work for action states that all young people have “the human right to benefit from an education that will meet their basic learning needs in the best and fullest sense of the term , an education that includes learning to know, to do, to live together and to be”, based on the four pillars of education in the report to UNESCO of the international commission on education for the twenty first century.

The four pillars in a life skill approach are the following:

Learning to know: It refers to both the acquisition of knowledge and use of knowledge that is acquiring the instruments of understanding. It includes the development of the faculties of memory, imagination, reasoning, problem solving and the ability to think in a coherent and critical way. Learning to know pre supposes learning to learn, calling up the power of concentration, memory and thought, so as to benefit from ongoing educational opportunities continuously arising formally and non-formally throughout life. It can be regarded as both a means and an end in learning itself in life.

As a means it serves to enable individual learners to understand the very least enough about the nature, about the human kind and about his or her environment and about society at large. As an end it enables the learner to experience the pressure of knowing, discovering, understanding as a process.

Learning to be: It recognizes a person as someone who acts and brings about change, and whose achievements can be judged in terms of her or his own value and objectives, whether or not we assess them in terms of some external criteria as well. It emphasizes the development of every child's personality so that he/she is able to act with greater autonomy, judgment and personal responsibility. The aim of development is the complete fulfillment of man in all richness of its personality. The complexity of its forms of expression and its various commitments as an individual member of a family and of a community and a citizen. Learning to be may therefore be interpreted in one way as learning to be human through acquisition of knowledge, skills and values, conducive to personality development in its intellectual, moral, in cultural and physical dimensions. This implies a curriculum aiming at cultivating qualities of imagination and creativity acquiring universally shared human values, developing human potentials, memory, reasoning, aesthetic sense, physical capacity and communication, social skills, developing critical thinking and exercising independent judgement, developing personal commitment and responsibility.

Learning to do: It is linked to what actions a person takes, and is closely related to practical skills, participate and cooperate with other people in all human activities. It is associated with vocational-technical education and work skills training. Learning to do calls for new type of skills, more behavioral than intellectual. It implies a shift from skill to competence, or a mix of higher order skills, specific to each individual. Learning to do emphasizes ability to communicate effectively with others; aptitude towards team work; social skills in building meaningful interpersonal relations; adaptability to changing the world of work and in social life; competency in transforming knowledge in to innovations and job creation; and readiness to take risks and resolve or manage conflicts.

Learning to live together: It denotes feeling concerned by others welfare and feeling an affiliation linked to a group, a category, a society and a culture. It implies development of such qualities as knowledge and understanding of self and others; appreciation of the diversity of human race and an awareness of the similarities between and the interdependence of all humans, empathy and co-operative social behavior in caring and sharing; respect of other people and other cultures and various system; capability of encountering others and resolving conflicts through dialogue and competency in working towards common objectives.

Life skill education for sustainable development

According to United Nations General Assembly sustainable development aims to maintain economic advancement and progress while protecting the long-term value of the environment, it provides a framework for the integration of environment policies and development strategies. Sustainable development means development of knowledge skills and values required to accomplish the needs of present generation without compromising with the ability of future generation to gratify their needs. Life skill training has the potential to strengthen various development initiatives and improve education by using skill-based approach so as to mold and shape the behaviour pattern of the children. Life skill inculcates the needed competencies for human development and in a way to develop positive behaviour in the lifestyle of the young people and make them confident enough to face the challenges of their day to day life. Life skill programmes are developmental initiatives that has most important value when working in collaboration with other developmental initiatives which supplement the health and educational programmes. Teaching life skill in relation to everyday life could form the foundation of life skills for the promotion of mental well-being and healthy interaction and develops adaptive social behaviour which help the individual to lead a holistic and fruitful life. Life skill based education encompasses the interactive process of teaching and learning which focuses on acquiring knowledge ,attitude, values and skills which support the positive behaviour of the learner that enable them to take up greater responsibility in their lives by making healthy life choices gaining greater resistance power and help them to lead a civilized human life.

It is essential that what students learn is relevant to them as individuals and members of society in their present and future contexts. It lies at the centre of educational process in enabling learners to become not only successful learning achievers at school but also responsible citizens, effective workers, Caring community members and lifelong learners in an increasingly interdependent world.

Conclusion

Education has to meet the challenges of a rapidly changing world. The school curriculum in the light of future challenges of the 21st century is expected to address the issues seriously. Life skill education can help to improve the well-being of individuals. The life skills are to be developed in the process of education. These life skills enable a person to live his life effectively purposefully, successfully and meaningfully. When knowledge is learned passively, without skills, it is often learned at a superficial level and therefore not readily transferred to new environments, deep understanding and accountability for the real world will occur only by embedding skills within knowledge domain, such that each enhances the other. In the present social scenario skills are the key to solving economic civic, and

global challenges and to engaging effectively in those spheres, then we must act upon the belief that using those skills to overhaul our education system is possible.

References

1. Dash, B.N (2003). Principles of Education. Neel Kamal Publications Pvt.Ltd: Hyderabad.
2. Narayana Swamy (2012). Life Skill Education- A Catalyst for Positive Development, Endeavours in Education 3 (1), 1-14.
3. Singh, Madhu (2003). Understanding Life Skills, UNESCO, Global Monitoring Report 2003-04.
4. UNICEF (2002). <http://www.unicef.org/programme/lifeskills/whatwhy/define.html>
5. UNICEF (2009). Essential Life Skills, <http://www.unicef.org>
6. WHO (1993) Promoting Health Through Schools Reports of WHO expert committee on comprehensive school Health Education and promotion, WHO, Technical Report Series 870, division of publishing, Geneva27, Switzerland